

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL JOINTS IN STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF GRP

*M. A. Serrano**, *A. Güemes***

*Dep. Construction and Manufacture Engineering. University of Oviedo (Spain)

**E.T.S.I.Aeronautics. Polytechnic University of Madrid (Spain)

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a survey of the problems that arise when mechanical joints are executed with composite materials constituted of polyester or vinylester reinforced with several weaves of fiber-glass.

The absence of data relative to the problems tackled in this survey demanded from the beginning to carry out some research which was mainly experimental, based on the data obtained from an extensive programme of tests, with the aim of including several characteristics of the joints that we tried to design.

Thus, a plan of tests was elaborated and developed which allowed us to analyze the influence that some design variables had on the strength of a mechanical joint using the materials considered and subjected to several kinds of efforts.

With the results obtained in the different tests, a series of tables and graphics were elaborated which allowed us to analyze and relate the different cases investigated and to suggest some valuable recommendations for a safe design of joints.

Keywords: mechanical joints; design; GRP laminates; test method.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites are of great interest for their application to structural elements given their well-known and widely recognized attractive features: good mechanical properties, considerable corrosion resistance, high dimensional stability, low weight, etc. All these specific properties make them very competitive when you compare them to classical materials.

Although the ideal situation for the designer would be to design monolithic structures, since it is far more advantageous for reasons of weight and mechanical simplicity, the integration of these elements in a structure very often demands the use of joining techniques, as a result of the size limitations imposed by the materials or the manufacturing process, or else due to the fact that it is necessary to have at one's disposal disassemble structures to transport, inspect or repair them.

As composite materials are more frequently used as primary structure components in industry in general it becomes necessary a more precise design of the mechanical joints that guarantees a safe transmission of efforts as well as a better use of the material.

The strength of mechanical joints in composites cannot be predicted supposing a plastic behaviour as in the case of ductile metals, and consequently design procedures utilized for the mechanical joints in metallic structural elements must be adapted to the properties of anisotropy, fragility and heterogeneous nature of composite materials.

The study proposed in this paper intends basically to analyze experimentally the influence a series of parameters exert on the joint behaviour of glass polyester and vinylester laminates. Consequently it is considered the effect of lay-up, resin type, joint type (single or double lap), joint geometry, hole size, washer size, load direction, laminate thickness, etc.

The joint efficiency results obtained for pin loaded multi-hole joints in double and single lap are presented for their comparison with the data obtained in single hole specimens loaded in double lap.

2. TEST DESCRIPTION

2.1. Description and characterization of the material

The material utilized was elaborated from prepregs of polyester and vinylester resins reinforced with eight unidirectional and plain weave fabrics of E-glass arranged in three symmetrical configurations with the following stacking sequences:

Laminate A: $(\pm 45^\circ / (0^\circ, 90^\circ) / \pm 45^\circ / (0^\circ, 90^\circ))_s$

Laminate B: $(0^\circ / (0^\circ, 90^\circ) / \pm 45^\circ / (0^\circ, 90^\circ))_s$

Laminate C: $(0^\circ_2 / \pm 45^\circ / 0^\circ)_s$

Three laminates of an approximate thickness of 1.5mm, 1.65mm and 2mm, respectively were prepared and cured in a hot plate press under a pressure of 3 Kpa and 90°C of temperature. From them the specimens used for the different tests were obtained. Fibre volume, measured by calcination and weighting was quite uniform $59\% \pm 2.5\%$ for the three laminates. Porosity was negligible $< 1\%$.

Tensile tests were carried out on the laminates in order to characterize them mechanically, being necessary to instrument the specimens used with bidirectional strain gauges. Elasticity modulus and longitudinal (L) and transverse (T) tensile strengths were obtained and presented in - Table 1 -.

2.2. Description of mechanical joint tests

In order to find out the influence a series of variables have on the mechanical strength of the joints, a plan of tests was elaborated in which single and multi-hole joints were considered separately.

2.2.1. Single hole joints

Pin-loaded specimens in double lap were tested. They presented the following initial design data: end distance $e=4d$ and width $w=4d$. The parameters for each of three laminates were:

-The use of intermediate washers - Figure 3 -. Configurations with and without washers were considered - Figure 1 -. A constant tightening torque of 20Nm was kept when we use the intermediate washers.

Figure 1. Configurations with and without washers.

-The resin type - Figure 3 -. Laminates elaborated from resin systems of polyester and vinylester were used.

-The hole diameter - Figure 3 -. Two different diameters $d=6\text{mm}$ and $d=8\text{mm}$ were studied.

-The washer outside diameter - Figure 4 -. Washers of $2d$, $2.5d$ and $3d$ were selected for each hole diameter.

-The laminate thickness - Figure 5 -. In order to know the influence of thickness, double laminates (2A, 2B and 2C) were prepared and tested.

-The load application angle - Figure 6 -. Specimens were tested in which the axis of the laminate were at an angle to the direction of the load transmitted by the joint of 0° , 15° , 30° , 45° and 90° .

-Bypass - Figure 7 -. Tests of by-pass loading with the free hole and with a idling bolt were done to evaluate the loss of strength that implies the reduction of the cross section.

2.2.2. Multi-hole joints

Five different types of multi-hole joints were tested for each of the three laminates studied, having always a washer diameter of $3d$:

-Double lap joint with two bolts in tandem - Figure 8 -. Hole diameters of $d=6\text{mm}$ and $d=8\text{mm}$ were considered. The pitch between holes was $p=4d$.

-Double lap joint with two bolts in a row - Figure 8 -. Specimens with a transverse pitch of $p=4d$ and widths of $w=8d$ and $w=10d$ were studied.

-Single lap joint with two bolts in tandem - Figure 8 -. The pitch was kept at $p=4d$.

Figure 2. Single lap multi-hole joint.

Finally, two single lap multi-hole configurations were prepared and tested in which the transverse pitch and end distance were maintained at $p=4d$ and $e=4d$ although the row pitch was stepped down to $p=2d$ - Figure 2 - as a result of the use of staggered rows:

-Joint with three bolts in two staggered rows - Figure 8 -.

-Joint with five bolts in two staggered rows - Figure 8 -.

3. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the data obtained from the tensile tests for the three laminates studied -Table 1 - we can deduce the clear differences that exist between the quasisotropic laminate (A) and the more directional ones, and we can observe how as the laminate becomes more directional, the differences between the

longitudinal and transverse elasticity modulus are increased, existing a similar tendency for the tensile strengths that range from not much more than 100 Mpa for the laminate C tested with a transverse tensile test to 899 Mpa for the same laminate submitted to a longitudinal tensile test.

Table 1. Tensile mechanical features of the laminates.

Laminate	$E_L(Gpa)$	$E_T(Gpa)$	$X_L(Mpa)$	$X_T(Mpa)$
A	19.8	19.8	370	370
B	36.4	19.6	638	274
C	40.4	11.2	899	104

For the mechanical joints tested, the results are shown in some graphics and in terms of the structural efficiency of the joint. The joint efficiency versus various parameters for the laminate A is shown in the first place - Figures 3 to 8 -, and subsequently, more briefly the most significant results corresponding to the other two laminates considered are discussed - Figures 9 to 11 -.

In this way we see that for the quasisotropic laminate, of all the parameters analyzed it was the incorporation of intermediate washers the most determinant one, producing an important increase in the efficiency of the joint - Figure 3 -, being reached with this measure a joint efficiency between 56% and 68% when joints were executed with only one bolt and with the basic design parameters ($w=4d$ and $e=4d$), which means to quadruple the joint efficiency shown for similar joints executed, however, without intermediate washers, for which the joint efficiency is below than 20%.

Other parameters considered were: the resin type - Figure 3 - which showed almost no influence; the hole diameter - Figure 3 -, which implied efficiencies slightly smaller for bigger diameters; the washer outside diameter - Figure 4 -, that when became bigger increased the load transmitted by the joint in an almost lineal way; the laminate thickness - Figure 5 -, which, when we duplicate it reduces efficiency slightly; or, lastly the load application angle - Figure 6 -, which shows how an increment of the angle produces a practically lineal reduction of efficiency not higher than 5%. All these parameters represent small influences (around 10% at worst) on the joint structural efficiency. For this reason, it would be enough for the joints executed with the quasisotropic laminate to duplicate locally the thickness in the joining area to have bigger efficiencies than 100%, thus obtaining a safe design of the joint.

In the tests of by-pass loading it was observed that with a idling bolt in spite of the fact that the bolt does not transfer any load, it maintains a high pressure on the washers and its beneficial effect is evident - Figure 7 -.

As for the multi-hole joints tested we found that, for the more isotropic laminate - Figure 8 -, there was a small increase in the joint efficiency when a joint with two bolts in tandem is used instead of a joint with only one bolt. For the rest of multiple joints we have that: with two bolts in a row and three or five bolts in two staggered rows, the joint efficiency falls to 50%; it then, becomes advisable for the design of these joints, apart from duplicating thickness locally, to increase slightly the pitch between bolts and the distances to the lateral edges, since tensile failures in the net section have been detected whereas in the case of single hole joints the failure was usually produced by bearing against the washer, or by bearing if the tested joint did not include intermediate washers. These net section failures cause loss of joint efficiency, as a result of the impossibility to exploit all the capacity of transmission of loads potentially available in the multi-hole joints.

In the case of more directional laminates B and C the tendencies are in general similar to the ones observed for the more isotropic laminate. The main parameter to increase the joint efficiency is still the incorporation of intermediate washers with small influences of the other variables if we except the load application angle, being suitable to point out some peculiarities:

a) When intermediate washers are used, is reached a joint efficiency between 30% and 37% for laminate B - Figure 9 - and between 20% and 26% for the more directional laminate C - Figure 10 -.

b) The load application angle shows bigger influence as the laminates are more directional. The joint efficiency decrease a 50% at worst for an angle of $\Theta = 90^\circ$ in laminate C - Figure 11 -.

c) In the case of multi-hole joints the absence of net section failures allows a better use of these arrangements, as the laminates become more directional, maintaining the joint efficiency always above 30% for laminate B and more than 25% for laminate C.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND DESIGN SUGGESTIONS

The conclusions obtained from this survey based on the results from more than 750 joints tested and supported by a high repetition of results as a guarantee of their representativeness, are logically dependent on the configurations of the laminates as a consequence of the material anisotropy. It is for this reason that we will refer separately to the measures that should be adopted to obtain a reliable design of the joints executed for each laminate. It is, nonetheless, clear that the use of intermediate washers improve substantially the joint behaviour for all the laminates.

In quasisotropic laminates with four diameters in width, end distance and pitch in multi-hole joints, we suggest in order to perform safe designs, to duplicate locally the thickness in the joint area. And only in the case of multi-hole joints it would be suitable either to increase slightly the pitch between holes or the lateral edges distances, or both things, to avoid failures in the net section.

For more directional laminates and as a result of a bigger influence upon them of the angle of application of the load that must transmit the joint, we suggest two ways to perform safe designs:

- a) To increase the thickness in the joint area until a joint efficiency of 100% is obtained.
- b) To insert some plies to obtain more isotropic laminates in the joint area, what would considerably improve the joint efficiency.

5. REFERENCES

1. Agarwal, B.L., *Static Strength Prediction of Bolted Joint in Composite Material*, AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS, 20th Structure, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, St.Louis, MD, April 1979, pp. 303-309.
2. Chang, F.K., Scott, R.A., and Springer, G.S., *Design of Composite Laminates Containing Pin Loaded Hole*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.18, 1984, pp.279-289.
3. Collings, T.A., *On the Bearing Strengths of CFRP Laminates*, Composites, July 1982, pp.241-252.
4. Crews, Jr, J.H. and Naik, R.A., *Bearing-Bypass Loading on Bolted Composite Joints*, AGARD CP-427, 1987.
5. Eriksson, I., *An Analysis Method for Bolted Joints in Primary Composite Aircraft Structure*, AGARD CP-427, 1987.
6. Garbo, S.P., and Ogonowski, J.M., *Effect of Variances and Manufacturing Tolerances on the Design Strength and Life of Mechanically Fastened Composite Joints*, AFWAL-TR-81-3041, Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratory, Dayton, Oh, Vol.1&2, April 1981.
7. Hart-Smith, L.J., *Mechanically Fastened Joints for Advanced Composites. Phenomenological Considerations and Simple Analyses*, Fourth Conf. on Fibrous Composites in Structural Design, Nov.1978.
8. Johnson, M. and Matthews, F.L., *Determination of Safety Factors for Use When Designing Bolted Joints in GRP*, Composites, April 1979, pp.73-76.

9. Kretsis, G., and Matthews, F.L., *The Strength of Bolted Joints in Glass Fibre/Epoxy Laminates*, Composites,16: pp. 92-102, 1985.
10. Lessard, L.B., *Bearing Failure of Composite Pinned Joints using Progressive Damage Modeling*, ICCM-8^o, pp.9E1-9E10, Honolulu, 15-19 July 1991.
11. Lessard, L.B., Poon, C.J., and Fahr, A. *Composite Pinned Joint Failure Modes Under Progressive Damage*, ECCM-5^o, pp. 49-54, Bordeaux, April 1992.
12. Matthews, F.L., *Joining Fibre Reinforced Plastics*, Barking, Essex, UK, Elsevier Applied Science Publishers, 1986, Chapter 2.
13. Matthews, F.L., *The Static Strength of Bolted Joints in Fibre Reinforced Plastics*, AGARD CP-427, 1987.
14. Murthy, A.V., Dattaguru, B., and Narayana, H.V.L., *Stress and Strength Analysis of Pin Joints in Laminated Anisotropic Plates*, Composite Structures 19, 1991 pp. 299-312.
15. Oplinger, D.W., *Behaviour of Mechanically Fastened Joints in Composite Structures*, Proceedings of a conference on Fibrous Composites in Structural Design, San Diego, California, Nov.14-17, 1978,pp.575-602.
16. Ramkumar, R.L., Saether, E.S., Appa, K. and Venkayya, V.B., *Strength Analysis of Mechanically Fastened Composite Structures*, AGARD CP-427, 1987.
17. Serrano, M.A., *Phenomenological Analysis of Mechanically Fastened Joints in Structural Elements of Composite Materials*, Dep. Construction and Manufacture Engineering, University of Oviedo, Spain, July 1992, PhD Thesis.
18. Soni, S.R., *Failure Analysis of Composite Laminates with a Fastener Hole*, Joining of Composite Materials, STP 749, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1981, pp. 145-164.
19. Stockdale, J.H., and Matthews, F.L., *The effect of Clamping Pressure of Bolt Bearing Loads in Glass Fiber-Reinforced Plastics*, Composites, Vol.7, Jan 1971,pp.34-38.
20. Whitney, J.M., Daniel, I.M., and Pipes, R., *Experimental Mechanics of Fiber Reinforced Composite Materials*, Prentice-Hall, Inc., New Jersey, 1982.

Figure 3. Effect of: washers, resin type and hole diameter for laminate A.

Figure 4. Effect of the washer diameter.

Figure 5. Effect of the laminate thickness.

Figure 6. Effect of the load application angle.

Figure 7. Traction bypass test

Figure 8. Efficiency in multi-hole joints for laminate A.

Figure 9. Effect of: washers, resin type and hole diameter for laminate B.

Figure 10. Effect of : washers, resin type and hole diameter for laminate C.

Figure 11. Effect of the load application angle for laminate C.